

Bravely fought the Queen: A Study of the voices against the suppression through patriarchal social system

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Abstract

Contemporary Indian literature discusses various taboo issues in the society. The playwright like Mahesh Dattani and many more modern dramatists set their microscopes to depict man's social and family relationships. Mahesh Dattani is the first Indian playwright to be awarded the prestigious Sahitya Akademi Award for his unique contribution to Indian Literature. His endeavor is different from earlier attempts at staging Indian Drama in English as he chooses to entertain his spectators, at the same time making aware of the hidden issues lying beneath the surface. Thematically, Dattani's plays belong to the existing times dealing with sexuality, gender issues, religious tension, class conflicts, homosexuality etc. Dattani makes an abundant use of the Indian mythology, rituals, Traditions, contemporary problems and elevates these themes to higher level touching the human chords that emanate love, happiness, sexual fulfillment and the problem of identity. The plays *Bravely fought the Queen* the issue of gays. It charts through the emotional, financial and sexual details of a modern-day Indian family. The Play portrays the clash between traditional and contemporary cultures that has created a new social landscape. The present paper would flash upon the thematic artistry of the play as well as the deep roots of the gay issue in the society.

Mahesh Dattani is the most powerful and potent dramatic voice in the present Indian English dramatic world. He has enriched and embellished tradition of Indian Drama with his experiments and innovations. With the arrival of Dattani on the literary scene, the scenario begins to change. Being the multifaceted literary and dramatic figure, he has given a new height and dimension to Indian English Drama. Michael Walling observes:

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His play fuses the physical and special awareness of the Indian theatre with the textual rigour of western models like Ibsen and Tennessee Williams.... they require public spaces in which the mingling of eastern and western influences can take place. (CP 229)

Bravely Fought the Queen is a powerful domestic tragedy of a women fighting against all the odds. It was first performed at the Sophia Bhava Hall, Mumbai on 2nd August, 1991. The play was subsequently performed by Border crossing, Uk in 1996 directed by Michael Walling and Mahesh Dattani. It deals with confined domestic freedom of the women and their seeking solace in their own way. The play focuses on ugly and harsh reality of our so-called normal life.

Dattani uses multi-level stage which helps in connecting the past with present and also contains certain symbols which indicate inner working of the minds of the characters. It was this kind of skill that made the production of the play a success not only in India but in England too. The whole play is beautifully presented in multi layered levels. The way he juxtaposes the past and the present, the imaginary level and the realistic level without breaking the flow of interest is simply marvelous. Every act is named as per the gender of the characters present therein. The act one is named as “The Women”. It speaks volume of women. It presents the emptiness and trauma in the lives of women of the Trivedi house and others. The act two is entitled as “The Men” and third is named as “Free for All”. The setting is same as in act one. Thumri also continues to play in the third act as in act one. The dramatist disproves the idea of varied spaces for men and women showing them human beings equal in all respects. The characters in the play are highly civilized and are influence by the urban society and are the resident of the cosmopolitan city. Though they are influenced by the western culture, Indian culture is blended with.

Indian culture considers marriage to be the supreme bond of a woman because it offers her salvation through her service to her husband. For her, Chastity is superior and preferable to life. This reduces her to a nonliving commodity that her father offers her as a gift to a man in marriage. She is denied love, enjoyment and education which are indispensable to the growth of the personality. A Hindu wife is honored as mother to bear progeny for a husband and as a partner to him in performing religious rites. So, Manu himself says, “Where women are honored there the Gods are pleased.”(170) But this type of treatment is rarely found in our patriarchal society.

Gayatri Spivak firmly said that all subjugated classes of society are not permitted to speak of their rights and duties. They are left to survive in the confined spaces of domesticity, kept in dark to bear the burden of patriarchy in silence and sobbing. They were treated as the second sex and were not permitted to participate in the activities of business world. Economically, culturally and biologically, they were treated as the incarnation of weakness and submissiveness. Their identity is defined only in context of the identity of their male counterparts. (Quoted Agrawal 69)

In Indian Society where religious values dominated women’s position and gave the status of ‘goddess’ to her, surviving with the ideals of sacrifice, love, sensibility, patience and resistance did not permit her freedom and independent identity. Shashi Deshpande in one of her novel comments, “a woman’s life they had told me, contain no choices.... The woman had no

choices but to submit and accept. And I had often wondered.... have they been without will or have their wills atrophied though a life time of disuse.”(Quoted Agrawal 71)

Barnard Shaw in his ideology of womanhood tried to promote that man and woman. Should be accepted as a part of the balanced scheme of things. He observed,

People are still full of the old idea that woman is a special creation but I am bound to say that of late years, she has been working extremely hard to eradicate that impression, and make one understand that woman is really only a man in petticoats, or if you like that a man is a woman without petticoats”.(Quoted Agrawal 71)

Mahesh Dattani interprets, woman as a human being gifted with equal sensibility to reciprocate the sensibility of their male counterparts. To the question, asked by Laxmi Subramanyam, Dattani replies,

They are human. They want something.

My only defence is to say that I am
not biased against woman.

The play *Bravely fought the Queen* referred “Queen” from the source of a translated Hindi poem about the Rani of Jhansi. Dolly Trivedi is a woman who has to fight a battle against a violent and unfaithful husband, and against a tyrannical mother-in-law who rules over her sons and daughters-in-laws with the weapon of her wealth even from her paralytic bed. The play opens on the view of the fashionable but ill-maintained living room of Jiten and Dolly Trivedi where Thumri is playing at the background. The action starts with the arrival of an unexpected visitor-Lalitha. She comes to Dolly’s house as suggested by her husband. Dolly has awful memory who has forgotten of Lalitha’s identity. She met her at the parties. But she didn’t remember that her husband’s name is Shridhar who works for Dolly’s husband and handles ReVa Tee account. Here Dattani has introduced a basic issue that of the lack of communication between husband and wife.

After sometime we come to know about ‘Baa’ Dolly’s mother-in-law and mother of Jiten and Nitin. Her room is upstairs-She calls Dolly by pressing the bell again and again. Her character creates some kind of tension and on air of authority in the house. there is also reference regarding Dolly’s daughter Daksha who never appears physically in the play. Her presence is felt throughout the play. It reminds us the past cruelty of Jiten with his wife Dolly.

Theafter, Alka enters into Dolly’s house. She is both sister and sister-in-law to Dolly as both have married in the same family-the Trevidies. Trevidi brothers have twin houses side by side-one for each brother in a posh suburb of Bangalore. Thus, both sister line right next door. Alka, we notice, is an alcoholic who helps herself to liberal quantities of rum, and it is hinted further that the two sisters have a secret lover in Kanhaiya, the nineteen years-old grandsons of a friend of the vacatinoning cook, who stay in the servant’s quarters outside the house. The presence of Lalitha is a contrast to the position of Dolly and Alka. She is isolated in her own way but she tries to seek a fulfillment in her obsessive love for her bonsais, a tiny tree with miniscule fruits growing on it. The bonsai is the single significant metaphor integrated in the text of the play. It’s bizarre shape, the ugly becomes the objective representation of the mental condition of different characters. In spite

of the diversity in the mental thinking, all three women try to escape the frustration of their spaces. Alka seeks a consolation in alcohol, Dolly develops a attraction for Kanhaiya, while the obsession of Lalitha transmutes her passion for bonsais.

The playing of *thumri* of Naina Devi pervades right from the beginning to the end of the play. It has also got very symbolic significance. Naina Devi was a great queen, but she loved to sing *thumri* which was practiced by the whore. She had strong urge for singing love songs. She followed her urge and passion without caring for the social criticism. With the support of her husband, she sang in the face of patriarchal dominating society. She was mistaken as for a *twaiif*. Eventually, she is recognized as the queen of *thumri*. Dolly also wants to be dressed in whore at the ball like Naina Devi, a paradigm of heroism.

The title of the play is used in an ironic way showing domestic struggle of the women of the Trivedi family. There is a popular poem in Hindi about Rani Lakshmbai of Jhansi, a courageous queen. She fought against the Britishers. Through this story, the dramatist focuses women's craving for love and freedom and the struggle they underwent in the play.

Alka: (interested) 'Jhansi Ki Rani'

Lalitha: Yes, but how did it go? (Remembers and recites) We'd heard her praises sung so often. So bravely fought the Rani of Jhansi. (CP: 295-96)

Lalitha suggests Dolly to dress up herself as the Rani of Jhansi, a brave queen. But Alka is more inclined at this suggestion and wants to join dressing herself as a brave queen. Baa, who has the stroke, is in her late sixties. She is bed-ridden. She wears white sari. Her husband was very violent person. She had been ill-treated by him. The memory of violent husband is still alive. Two things are harassing to Alka and Dolly the bell and Baa's loud mouth. The play seeks to presents women's exploitation by the male. Alka is ill treated by her husband and by her own brother, Praful. She exclaims:

...I can't forget what they did to me! Our brother is a cheat! He lied about our father to them. And he lied to me! He lied to me by not telling me..... (CP 256)

Alka narrates past painful treatment given to her by Praful. Once, Alka came home on scooter of a neighbor's son. Annoyed by this, Praful dragged her into the kitchen without saying a word. He pushed her face in front of burning stove and burnt her hair. Despite his brutality, Dolly considers Praful as a very ideal person. It is learnt that Praful and Nitin were close friends since college days. Nitin also treated her badly by driving out of house for some time. There is a mystery regarding an old woman. There are many references of coming old woman again and again. Whenever she comes, they talk to wake up the watchman; the watchman is so sleepy that he wakes only when he hears horns of his *sahib's* car.

The play also highlights romantic story of Dolly and Kanhaiya, a teenager. Alka, in the presence of Lalitha, narrates the love-scene between Dolly and Kanhaiya in association with Naina Devi's *thumri*. It is quite shocking and humorous that Dolly is also interested in listening to the narration of her romance with Kanhaiya. She feels joy and embarrassment at the same time. Actually, interpolated tale of Kanhaiya, attractive cook who might or might not present also

functions as the powerful symbol which denotes disappointment, emptiness and trauma in the women of the Trivedi house hold. Alka and Lalitha have drunk excessively. Alka keeps on speaking under the influence of intoxication. How women behave when they are alone and guarded.

Further action explores men's business and world outside. The Trivedi brothers are having financial agency and Shridhar is working with them. There is a discussion on market survey for ReVa Tee advertisement made by Shridhar. The model is alright, but they have failed to understand women's desire. Reva Tee advertisement is suggestive and symbolic. The failure of ReVa Tee advertisement symbolizes that the men have failed to understand and recognize the feminine self and justice as human being. Dissatisfied with result of the ReVa Tee survey, Shridhar wants to make another presentation, but Jiten opposes the idea, calling it a great campaign. He says that they are of the women's opinions. They have little weight in the marketing world as they don't have buying power.

Jiten: Screw the survey! You know who you should have tested it out on? Men!

Shridhar: Men!

Jiten: Yes! Men would want to buy it for their women! That's our market. Men would want their women dressed up like that. And they have the buying power. Yes! So there's no point in asking a group of screwed-up women what they think of it. They'll pretend to feel offended and say, 'oh, we are always being treated like sex objects'. (CP 276)

Thus, Jiten doesn't respect views and opinions of women considering them as secondary human being or merely subordinate to their male counter parts. The play is portrait of sexual, moral, and financial fall in the lives of the Trivedi brothers. The play also shows how addiction of prostitution to the husband empties joy and happiness of marital relationship between husband and wife. Jiten and Shridhar are the pleasure seekers in prostitutions. They bring the outside women even at their office for gratifying the street party desires. The comfortable sofa is kept for this dirty purpose. As a result of this, their wives feel boredom and unhappiness in their marital lives. The play presents the shifting Indian values and dramatizes conflict between traditional and contemporary cultures.

The end of the play brings all men and women face to face. They are confronted and exposed to reality. In the third act, Jiten and Nitin come home to find Alka all wet and muddy as she has just danced in the rain and injured herself. Both are shocked to see her in an impolite look. Jiten stares at Alka and tells Nitin to ask her what she was doing outside in the rain.

Jiten: Ask her what she was doing outside in the rain.

Alka: I don't know! I don't know what I was doing outside. Aren't there times when you don't know what you are doing? (To Nitin) What's the harm in that? Huh? (No response) Tell me. What's the harm? (CP 299-300)

Baa is now, aged but the past ill memory of her husband is still fresh with her. She was brutally beaten up by her husband. He was a demon like person in both appearance and intention. Baa tells Lalitha:

“Ten years old and he is afraid of the dark. Afraid to sleep in the dark. Afraid of his father - who is as black as night!” (CP 272)

Further, Baa narrates the brutal behavior of her husband.

Baa: You hit me? I only speak the truth and you hit me? Go on. Hit me again. The children should see what a demon you are. Aah! Jitu! Nitin! Are you watching? See your father! (Jerks her face as if she’s been slapped.) No! No! Not on the face! What will the aaaah! (Covers her face weakly as her scream turns silent and the light on her fades out). (CP 278)

Jiten is like his father, violent and drunkard. He is very violent with his wife Dolly as his father was with his wife, Baa. He hit badly even when Dolly was pregnant.

Dolly: And you hit me! Jitu, you beat me up! I was carrying Daksha and you beat me up! (CP 311)

But Jiten blames Baa. He bit her as Baa’s provocation. She denied Daksha was their blood. She called Dolly a whore and Jitu believed her words. Baa puts blame on Praful. He lied to her. Dolly gives expression to her pent-up pain and anguish at the end of the play to Jiten.

Dolly: Fifteen years ago. Hardly married for a year. Praful comes to visit us. The same day, your mother receives a letter from her cousin in Ahmedabad what fate! It had to be the same day! And it had to be the crucial month for me! What was in that letter? Our whole history. Including the portion which Praful hadn’t told you about. (CP 311)

Neither of the brothers is willing to admit the guilt. They blame other. Jiten blames Baa. Baa blames Praful and other and Nitin blames upon Praful.

Jiten: (sobbing) No! No! (Points to Baa’s room) She made me do it! She did it!

Dolly: No! Oh no! I will not let you get away easily! They were your hands hitting me! Your feet kicking me! It’s in your blood! It’s in your blood to do bad! (CP 312)

The play also exposes the male prejudice and woman as the colonized subordinate section of male dominant Indian society. Baa and Dolly are the worst victims of the conventional and cruel attitude of their husbands. They are meted with injustice and ill treatment at the hands of their male counter parts. In Dattani’s play, battle is fought in the house. In this play, the house of Trivedi brothers seem to be the arena. In fact, female character of prosperous homes raises their voices against the suppression and suppression through patriarchal social system. The play also depicts the issue of homosexuality in a very bold manner. The play also throws light on the suffering of the wife due to her husband turning out to be a guy. Alka’s anguish and agony is aggravated when she comes to know that Nitin, her husband, has homosexual relationship with her own brother, Praful. She has become the victim of her own brother’s gay relationship. Her brother was having homosexual relationship with Nitin. Hence, he gets her sister married with his partner to continue his relationship in a smoother and longer way. Alka retorts and pours her anger against her brother for making her scapegoat. Her wrath and anger is well expressed in the following outburst.

Alka: Our saint of a brother used to warm us against men like you. (Points to Jiten) And what does he do? The saint gives his sister to the sinister and disappears! (Makes a motion of wiping her

hands) Finished. Matter over. Or is it? The saint has another sister who is (slaps her own face) bad, bad, bad. He beats her till she gets better. And he has this friend. A best friend! The sinister's brother turns out to be his best friend. Not such a coincidence. (CP: 300)

The play *Bravely Fought the Queen* encompasses issue of gayism along with the main theme of exploitation of educated women in urban society. On account of dry marital life, Alka has become a boozier. She has drunk heavily and lied on the sofa. Looking at her huddled figure, at the end of the play Nitin admits;

Oh! But how ashamed he me feel after! He made me cry each time! That was a game he played. And I-I was whom? ... He told me that you knew. That he about me. And that it didn't matter to you. You only wanted the -I am sorry. It wasn't my fault. (Moves to her and slowly covers her face with the blanket) But now, you will have to sleep. You mustn't wake (CP: 314-15)

Thus, the play ends with Nitin's confessional soliloquy. He is anxious to meet dark auto driver. Dattani detects virgin issues and presents through his theatrical mechanism in an innovative fashion.

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